

Eastern England SDE Researcher Statistical Disclosure Control SOP

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Documentation context

This document is shared with researchers via the Eastern England Knowledgebase. All internal links are provided as appendices and external links provided as documentation. Other Trusted Research Environments (TREs) will be able to use this SOP as a template

for their own approach, but the specific technical implementation of file egress, airlock manager and researcher interaction will need to be updated to capture the steps in that specific TRE. The document covers preparation of data for egress, as well as the integration of ACRO in the workflow of egress where appropriate.

1 Research outputs egress review

All research outputs to egress from the Secure Data Environment are reviewed by two airlock managers, following the “Four-Eyes” principles. The purpose of this review is to ensure no output carries undue risk to individuals or classes of people being identified from the outputs.

1.1 Preparing Your Outputs Before Requesting Egress

Before submitting an egress request, you must ensure that your outputs have been appropriately reviewed for disclosure risk.

Egress from the Secure Data Environment (SDE) is subject to Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC). The purpose of SDC is to ensure that no released output enables identification of individuals, organisations, or small groups, either directly or indirectly.

As a researcher, you are responsible for applying appropriate disclosure control to your outputs before initiating an egress request.

1.2 Understanding Disclosure Risk

When preparing outputs for release, you should consider the following forms of disclosure risk:

1.2.1 Primary disclosure

Direct disclosure occurs when an individual or one of their attributes can be directly identified from a cell, value, or data point. Residual disclosure occurs when suppressed or hidden values can be recalculated or inferred, for example by differencing totals, subtotals, or related outputs.

1.2.2 Class disclosure (attribute disclosure)

Occurs when a small group is identifiable and sensitive attributes about that group can be inferred, even if individuals are not directly identifiable.

1.2.3 Secondary disclosure

Occurs when an output appears safe in isolation but becomes disclosive when combined with previously released outputs from the same project.

All three forms of risk must be considered before submitting outputs for release.

Researchers are encouraged to review the relevant output type in [Statbarn](#) to better understand the inherent disclosure risks associated with their chosen statistical method or visualisation. [Statbarn](#) provides guidance on typical risk elements, recommended checks, and appropriate mitigation approaches that can support preparation prior to submitting an egress request.

1.3 Things To Check Before Submitting

You should review your outputs and confirm that:

1. Small or sparse groups are not identifiable
2. Appropriate aggregation, suppression, or rounding has been applied where required
3. Tables cannot be differenced to reveal suppressed values
4. Excessive stratification does not create rare or uniquely identifiable subgroups
5. Visualisations do not expose identifiable outliers or rare combinations
6. Narrative text does not describe unique or rare cases in a way that enables identification
7. No row-level or record-level data is included
8. The output remains non-disclosive when considered alongside prior releases from your project

More in depth information about disclosure risks and statistical disclosure control can be found in:

- [Eastern England Disclosure control training slides](#)
- [Section A of the Safe Data Access Professionals SDC handbook](#)

1.4 Using ACRO (Where Applicable)

If your statistical analysis in Python, R can be wrapped with ACRO, your outputs should be generated through the ACRO workflow prior to egress. [The SACRO tools website](#) provides deeper information on how to use ACRO

Please be aware that the use of ACRO does not replace your responsibility to consider contextual, class or secondary disclosure risks. You must still review your outputs to ensure they are appropriate for release.

Where ACRO is not applicable to your output type, you must ensure that manual SDC checks have been applied before submitting your request.

2. Information Required from Researcher for Egress Request

To support efficient review and minimise back-and-forth with the airlock manager, your request should clearly describe:

- Description of the output type (e.g. aggregated tables, summary statistics, figures)
- The intended purpose of the release (e.g. manuscript submission, presentation, report)
- A brief rationale explaining how the output aligns with the approved project scope and analytical objectives
- The disclosure control approach applied (e.g. aggregation, suppression, rounding)
- Any contextual considerations relevant to secondary disclosure
- Confirmation of ACRO use (where applicable)

Example:

Field	Description
Output Type	Table – Ethnic background by age
Dataset Source	National Pupil Database 2020
Sample Size	N = 1000 (Minimum subgroup size 10)
Variables	Ethnicity, Age
Disclosure Techniques	Suppression of cells < 10, age groups in 5 – year bands
Cohort Disclosure	Pupils aged 16 -20 attending schools in England
Purpose of Output	Show ethnicity diversity patterns across teenage groups

The current airlock process does not allow you to provide more than 250 characters in the description. Please provide this information in a README file alongside the research outputs you wish to egress. This additional context will allow airlock managers to more efficiently assess your outputs.

Requests that do not include sufficient explanation will be returned for clarification, which can delay the decision-making process.

2.1 Please follow the steps below to Egress data from the platform

If you have not used the airlock before, it will need to be enabled for your account. Please raise a ticket through our service desk to request airlock permissions for egress.

1. The researcher prepares outputs within the secure environment and places them in the designated egress location. Outputs must include a README file describing the contents, purpose, and any Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) measures applied.
2. The researcher opens the Data Transfer and Review Component (DTRC) from the Virtual Desktop environment and logs in using organisational credentials.
3. The researcher completes the transfer details, including:
 - i. A clear and meaningful transfer name
 - ii. A brief description of the outputs

- iii. Selection of the project egress source and destination locations
 - iv. Specify the files or folders to be transferred, if required. If left blank, all files in the selected source location will be included.
5. Once submitted, the outputs are moved to a controlled review (quarantine) location where they cannot be modified during the review process.
 6. A service desk ticket is automatically generated, including the request details (project, user, unique transfer id)
 7. The airlock manager reviews the request using appropriate disclosure control methods (ACRO/SACRO or manual SDC checks), ensuring both disclosure risk and alignment with the approved project scope are assessed.
 8. Following approval, the outputs are released, and the researcher is notified with access to the final output files. If rejected, the researcher must revise and resubmit the request.

Glossary

ACRO (Automated Checking of Research Outputs) – A tool used to apply automated statistical disclosure control checks to outputs in Python or R, supporting safer and more standardised output preparation.

Airlock manager – An authorised reviewer responsible for assessing outputs for disclosure risk and governance alignment before approving or rejecting egress requests.

Attribute Disclosure (Class Disclosure) – Risk that sensitive characteristics of a small identifiable group can be inferred, even when individuals are not directly identified.

DTRC (Data Transfer and Review Component) – The system used to submit, manage, and review data egress requests within the Secure Data Environment.

Disclosure Risk – The likelihood that released outputs could reveal sensitive information about individuals or groups, directly or indirectly.

Egress – The process of transferring outputs from the Secure Data Environment to an external location following disclosure review.

Four-Eyes Principle – A governance approach requiring two independent reviewers to assess outputs before approval to ensure consistency and risk mitigation.

Primary Disclosure – Direct identification of an individual or attribute from a specific value, or indirect identification through residual calculation of suppressed data.

Quarantine (Controlled Review Location) – A secure holding area where submitted outputs are stored during review and cannot be modified by the researcher.

README File – A supporting document describing output contents, purpose, and disclosure control methods, used to assist airlock managers in review.

Residual Disclosure – Risk that suppressed values can be recalculated using totals, subtotals, or related outputs.

Secondary Disclosure – Risk arising when outputs appear safe individually but become disclosive when combined with other released data.

Statistical Disclosure Control (SDC) – A framework of techniques (e.g. suppression, aggregation, rounding) used to ensure outputs are safe for release.

Statbarn – A guidance resource that provides information on disclosure risks and recommended mitigation techniques for different types of statistical outputs.

Stratification – Breaking data into subgroups (e.g. by age, gender), which can increase disclosure risk if groups become too small.

Suppression – The removal or masking of values (e.g. cells below a threshold) to prevent identification of individuals.

Virtual Desktop Environment (VDI) – The secure interface through which researchers access the SDE and perform analysis and egress activities.